

Quantitative Treatment of Substituent Effects in the Electrochemical Reduction of Arylazopyrazoles

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Electrochemical behaviour of some azo compounds have been studied during the last few decades¹. However, heterocyclic azo compounds have not received much attention^{2,4}. A literature survey reveals the absence of systematic electrochemical study on biologically important alkyl substituted arylazopyrazoles. In view of the fact that physiological activity of a molecule is closely related to its redox behaviour in the cell membrane⁵, it was planned to study the redox behaviour of 1-(carboxymethyl)pyridinium-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4-arylazopyrazoles (1).

Results and Discussion

All 1-(carboxymethyl)pyridinium-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4-arylazopyrazoles exhibited a single, well-defined, 2-electron polarographic wave, the height of which was constant within the whole pH range studied. Polarographic characteristics are given in Table 1. The characteristics of polarographic waves were determined at various temperatures and different heights of mercury column. The limiting current was found to be dependent on height of mercury column and a straight plot of i_d vs $\sqrt{h}$ and i_d vs concentration indicated diffusion-controlled nature of the electrode process. The low value of temperature coefficient ($\sim 1.56\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$) further confirmed the diffusion-controlled⁶ nature of the electrode process. The shift of half-wave potential towards more negative potential with increasing concentra-

tion of the depolariser (0.5×10^{-4} – 2.0×10^{-4} M) and log plot confirmed the irreversible nature of the electrode process.

The $E_{1/2}$ shifted towards negative potential with the rise in pH of the solution. The plots of $-E_{1/2}$ vs pH were linear upto pH 7.6 with slopes in the range 0.065–0.071 V/pH. After pH 7.6 there was practically constancy in half-wave potential becoming constant with pH. The pH at which two linear segments intercept represents the pK value. The shift of $E_{1/2}$ with increasing pH indicated the involvement of protons in the reduction and from this it was inferred that the proton transfer precedes the main electrode process⁷. Above pH 7.6, constant $E_{1/2}$ values indicated reduction of unprotonated species. Similar dependence of half-wave potential on pH has also been reported by other workers⁸ for analogous systems. A comparison of limiting current of 1-(carboxymethyl)pyridinium-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4-arylazopyrazoles indicates that most of the compounds are reduced by consuming similar number of electrons.

The complete controlled potential electrolysis of the parent compound(s) at the plateau potential (-1.4 V) at various pH using the mercury pool cathode consumed 2.0 ± 0.20 electrons (Table 2). The colour of the starting material faded out at the end of the completely reduced solution.

TABLE I—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF SOME SUBSTITUTED-1-(CARBOXYMETHYL)PYRIDINIUM-3-AMINOPHENYL-5-METHYL-4-ARYLAZOPYRAZOLES

pH = 6.5, concn = 1.0×10^{-4} M

R	M p *	$-E_{1/2}$	i_d	α_n	$\frac{dE_{1/2}}{dpH}$, V	I	$\Delta E_{1/2}$	P	$K_{1h}^{\dagger}$
	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	V	μA		$\frac{V}{pH}$		V		cm s^{-1}
H	100	0.54	0.40	1.22	0.067	0.26	0.00	1.10	1.6×10^{-7}
2-CH ₃	80	0.55	0.40	1.08	0.065	0.26	0.01	1.20	2.3×10^{-7}
3-CH ₃	125	0.55	0.45	1.12	0.065	0.29	0.01	1.09	9.3×10^{-6}
4-CH ₃	100	0.57	0.45	1.08	0.070	0.29	0.02	1.12	5.4×10^{-7}
2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	95	0.56	0.40	1.12	0.065	0.26	0.02	1.20	9.2×10^{-7}
2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	140	0.56	0.40	1.08	0.065	0.26	0.02	1.12	6.3×10^{-7}
4-C ₂ H ₅	111	0.59	0.45	1.10	0.065	0.29	0.05	1.12	5.4×10^{-7}
4-C ₄ H ₉	100	0.60	0.50	1.20	0.067	0.32	0.06	1.10	6.4×10^{-7}
4-C ₅ H ₁₁	160	0.62	0.45	1.22	0.071	0.29	0.08	1.21	8.2×10^{-6}
4-C ₆ H ₁₃	90	0.62	0.45	1.08	0.060	0.29	0.08	1.21	3.2×10^{-7}
4-C ₇ H ₁₅	98	0.63	0.40	1.08	0.067	0.26	0.09	1.10	8.4×10^{-7}

* All m ps are uncorrected

TABLE 2—VALUES OF n DETERMINED BY COULOMETRY FOR THE REDUCTION OF 1-(CARBOXYMETHYL)PYRIDINIUM-3-AMINOPHENYL- 5-METHYL-4-ARYLAZOPYRAZOLES AT MERCURY POOL ELECTRODE

pH	Potential V	n exptl.
4.0	-1.40	2.15
6.5	-1.60	2.20
8.0	-1.60	2.10

Linear sweep and cyclic voltammetry : Voltammetry of the arylazopyrazoles was performed at glassy carbon electrode in the pH range 2.0–12.0. Some typical cyclic voltammograms are shown in Fig. 1. The voltammograms

Fig 1 Typical cyclic voltammograms of 1-(carboxymethyl)pyridinium-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4-arylazopyrazoles at pH (1) 6.5, (2) 7.8, concn. = $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $v = 50 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$

were recorded at various scan rates ($20\text{--}200 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$). All the compounds showed only one voltammetric reduction peak at any scan rate. The cathodic peak potential of the peak shifted towards negative potentials with increasing scan rate as expected for irreversible electrode process⁹. The plot of i_p vs $v_{1/2}$ was also found to be straight line passing through the origin corroborating diffusion-controlled¹⁰ nature of electrode process as has been examined in conventional polarographic studies. Voltammetric characteristics are compiled in Table 3.

Keeping in view the feasibilities^{2,3} of the site of reduction, it was concluded that --N=N-- is more susceptible² to reduction as its reduction occurs at low potential. Reduction of azo compounds by two electrons giving corresponding hydrazo derivatives has also been reported by other workers¹¹. Nygard¹² reported that reduction of azo benzene gave a reversible two electron wave at low concentration and low pH. The single irreversible wave for azo compounds under study may be attributed to the terminal bulky pyrazole moiety.

As the number of electrons involved in the overall reduction is two and the number of protons involved in the rate-determining step is one and only one hydrazo product is obtained after exhaustive electrolysis, the mechanism shown in Scheme 1 may be proposed for the reduction of these compounds at d.m.e. and g.c. electrodes :

Scheme 1

The solution after controlled potential electrolysis gave negative test for amino group, thereby confirming that after reduction of --N=N-- to --NH--NH-- further reduction to aromatic amine is not taking place. Furthermore, the above mentioned electrolysed solution did not give any polarographic or cyclic voltammetric peak. This mechanism gets valid support through other earlier work¹³

TABLE 3—CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF SOME 1-(CARBOXYMETHYL)PYRIDINIUM-3-AMINOPHENYL-5-METHYL-4-ARYLAZOPYRAZOLES

pH = 6.5, concn. = $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $v = 50 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$

R	$-E_p$ V	i_p μA
H	0.56	3.00
2-CH ₃	0.57	2.80
3-CH ₃	0.58	2.80
4-CH ₃	0.59	2.85
2,3-(CH ₃) ₂	0.58	2.70
2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	0.59	2.70
4-C ₂ H ₅	0.62	2.80
4-C ₄ H ₉	0.63	2.90
4-C ₅ H ₁₁	0.64	2.75
4-C ₆ H ₁₃	0.65	2.75
4-C ₇ H ₁₅	0.66	2.70

Effect of substituents : For the application¹⁴ of the modified Hammett equation, the electrode process in the electroreduction of all analogous compounds must be identical¹⁵. In the present series of compounds this is obvious from the practically identical value of $dE_{1/2}/dpH$ and α_n (Table 1). Accordingly the half-wave potentials of these compounds were plotted against Hammett substituent constants¹⁵ (σ) resulting in a linear relationship (Fig. 2). All alkyl substituents except *ortho* and disubstituted derivatives fit in a straight-line. The deviation in the case of *ortho* and disubstituted derivatives, viz. 2-CH₃, 2,3-(CH₃)₂ and 2,5-(CH₃)₂ from the regression line can be accounted for on the basis of steric hindrance to coplanarity¹⁴.

The specific reaction constant (ρ) was found to be 0.19 V and its positive sign indicated the nucleophilic nature of the electrode process. Furthermore, this value of ρ is in

Fig 2 plot of $-E_{1/2}$ vs σ of 1-(carboxymethyl)pyridinium-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4-arylazopyrazoles at pH 6.5, concn = 1.0×10^{-4} M

good agreement with the reported¹⁵ values for similar systems. The observed linear relationship of $E_{1/2}$ vs σ indicated that the substituents appreciably affected the reduction of azo group by polar and mesomeric effects.

Polarographic *ortho*-shift (Δ_o) expressed by the relation¹⁷,

$$\Delta_o = (E_{1/2})_{o-R} - (E_{1/2})_{p-R}$$

was determined at different pH values for methyl group and found to be positive (Table 1). The positive value of the polarographic *ortho*-shift indicated that reduction is facilitated in the *ortho*-derivative in comparison to the *para*-substituted derivative. The additive effect of substituents¹⁴ for disubstituted derivative was determined. As there was appreciable shift in $E_{1/2}$, it was found that 2,3-(CH₃)₂ and 2,5-(CH₃)₂ did not show additivity of 2 : 3 and 2 : 5 shifts.

Effect of solvent composition : The percentage of the solvent can affect the polarographic characteristics¹⁶. With the increase in the percentage of DMF in the present reaction series, the $E_{1/2}$ shifted towards more negative potential along with decrease in i_d (Table 4). Besides the possible medium effect (i.e. increase in pH or pK by DMF) on $E_{1/2}$, the additional shift in $E_{1/2}$ may be ascribed to a decrease in adsorbability and hence surface concentration of the depolariser with an increasing percentage of DMF in aqueous organic mixture. Obviously, decreased surface concentration would retard the electrode process¹⁷ resulting in decrease in $E_{1/2}$ and i_d .

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION ON THE POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF 1-(CARBOXYMETHYL)PYRIDINIUM-3-AMINOPHENYL-5-METHYL-4-ARYLAZOPYRAZOLES

pH = 6.5, concn. = 1.0×10^{-4} M

DMF %	$-E_{1/2}$ V	i_d μ A
30	0.54	0.40
40	0.59	0.36
50	0.67	0.30
60	0.74	0.22
70	0.81	0.16
80	0.90	*

Effect of cations and anions : For studying the effect of the size of the cation on the characteristics of polarographic waves, polarograms were recorded using LiCl, NaCl, KCl, KBr, KI, KNO₃ and (C₂H₅)₄NBr as supporting electrolytes. Half-wave potential shifted towards more negative potential with increase in size of the cation without influencing the wave-height and the slope of wave (Table 5). In cases where $E_{1/2}$ is independent of ψ_1 or ionic strength for a particular supporting electrolyte, it could vary from one electrolyte to the other. However, increase in the size of cations led to the decrease in ψ_1 , making the reduction more difficult with the net result that $E_{1/2}$ shifted towards more negative potential. But in case of (C₂H₅)₄NBr, limiting current also decreased (Table 5). This behaviour can be at-

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF DIFFERENT SUPPORTING ELECTROLYTES ON POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF 1-(CARBOXYMETHYL)PYRIDINIUM-3-AMINOPHENYL-5-METHYL-4-ARYLAZOPYRAZOLES

pH = 6.5, concn = 1.0×10^{-4} M

Supporting electrolyte	$-E_{1/2}$ V	i_d μ A
LiCl	0.51	0.40
NaCl	0.53	0.40
KCl	0.54	0.40
KBr	0.54	0.40
KI	0.54	0.40
KNO ₃	0.54	0.40
(C ₂ H ₅) ₄ NBr	0.58	0.35

tributed to preferential adsorption of tetramethylammonium cation to that of the depolariser. This was further evident from the fact that the limiting current decreased only with this cation and not with others, viz. Li⁺, Na⁺, K⁺ which are not preferentially adsorbed due to high adsorbability of these compounds. It is reported¹⁸ that adsorption lowered the concentration of the depolariser on the electrode surface as well as produced a different atmosphere for the electron transfer by change of the double layer structure. The combined effect of these two parameters would result in lowering of rate of electrode process, consequently shifting the $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative potential with decrease in diffusion current. A further check was made by taking a polarogram using supporting electrolyte having a common cation and different anions

viz. KBr, KI, KNO₃. As expected no change in $E_{1/2}$ and i_d was observed (Table 5) as the half-wave potential of the compounds was on the negative side of the electrocapillary maxima.

Experimental

Polarograms were recorded on an Elico CL-25 polarograph at $25 \pm 1^\circ$. The capillary had a flow rate of 1.75 mg s^{-1} and drop-time 3.20 s at a zero applied potential using saturated calomel electrode in 1.0 M KCl solution at a height of 65 cm of mercury column. The pH measurements were carried out on an Elico CL-15 pH meter. Stock solutions ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) of all arylazopyrazoles (Table 1) were prepared in purified dimethylformamide (A.R.). A solution mixture (cell content) of the depolariser (1.0 ml), DMF (2.0 ml) (which was necessary to prevent precipitation), 1.0 M KCl (1.0 ml) and the appropriate B.R. buffers (pH 2–12; 6.0 ml) was taken in the polarographic cell and was deaerated by passing purified nitrogen gas for ~10 min and corrections for residual current were made in all the cases. Temperature coefficient was calculated by Nejedly's method¹⁹. Cyclic voltammetric studies were carried out on a BAS CV-27 cyclic voltammograph in connection with Omnigraph 2000 x-y/t recorder. A three-electrode cell having Ag/AgCl as reference, glassy electrode as working and platinum as auxiliary electrode was used for the purpose. Number of electrons involved in the overall electrode process was evaluated by microcoulometry and controlled potential electrolysis at BAS CV-27 coulometer.

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